

Study on the Effectiveness of Chinese Cultural Dissemination in Korea: An Empirical Analysis Based on a Questionnaire Survey

Na LIU¹, Ying RU², and Jianhua TANG³

¹*Institute of Hermeneutics, Guangdong University of Foreign Studies, E-mail: youna1105@hotmail.com*

²*School of Foreign Studies, Chang'an University, E-mail: ruying0509@gmail.com*

³*Shien-Ming Wu School of Intelligent Engineering, South China University of Technology, E-mail: jtang4@scut.edu.cn*

Abstract: Amidst the growing trend of global integration, Chinese cultural dissemination on an international scale has emerged as a significant concern. South Korea, being a neighboring country of China, has a rich history of cultural interactions between the two nations. However, in the present era, there are still obstacles to effectively promote Chinese culture and establish a strong connection with the Korean people. This paper aims to examine the level of knowledge and interest that Koreans have in Chinese culture by conducting a questionnaire survey. Additionally, it seeks to assess the effectiveness of dissemination and provide recommendations for enhancement of Chinese cultural dissemination.

Key words: Chinese culture, cultural dissemination, South Korea, questionnaire

1. Introduction

Intercultural communication and exchange play a crucial role in contemporary international relations. Culture serves as both a symbolic representation of a country's identity and a significant demonstration of its influence. The rich Chinese culture, spanning over 5,000 years, has captivated global interest due to its distinctive art, philosophy, history, language, and traditional customs (Hu & McLean, 2020).

South Korea, due to its geographical proximity to China, has a rich history of cultural interactions with its neighbor. Since the Han Dynasty, Chinese cultural elements—such as Confucianism, Chinese characters, and tea culture—has influenced South Korea through the Korean Peninsula. In recent years, cultural exchanges have intensified, leading to more frequent and interactive engagements (Lee, 2020). These extensive exchanges have made Chinese culture increasingly accessible to international audiences via films, TV dramas, literature, art exhibitions, and Confucius Institutes. South Korea regards aspects of Chinese culture, including Chinese characters and Confucianism, as part of its own heritage and envisions contributing to their future development (Pu, 2002). The Confucius Institute in South Korea effectively promotes martial arts culture (Piao & Du, 2010). Additionally, some South Korean film directors incorporate Chinese elements into their films, recognizing and appreciating Chinese culture. Films co-directed by Chinese and South Korean filmmakers are particularly well-received, appreciated for their cross-cultural storytelling, historical contexts, and cultural exchanges (Jin, 2020; Liu, 2019).

However, Chinese cultural dissemination in South Korea has encountered obstacles. Political and economic factors have recently caused fluctuations in the historically strong relations between the two countries. Incidents such as the THAAD deployment have led to strained relations and intermittent interruptions in cultural exchanges. Korean media reports on China exhibit diverse opinions, reflecting the complex and multifaceted attitudes of the Korean public towards China. There are significant challenges to effectively spreading Chinese culture and enhancing its impact on the Korean population. For instance, some South Korean films and TV dramas distort history, demonize Chinese cities, and vilify Chinese people, resulting in inaccurate, negative, and derogatory portrayals of Chinese culture (Li & Yu, 2023). Additionally, despite their popularity in Korean academia, classic Chinese literature like *A Dream in Red Mansions* and traditional culture like Mazu have received little attention among the general public due to cultural and religious reasons (Zheng, 2019).

Efficiently disseminating Chinese culture globally has become a significant concern, as it enhances a country's influence, supports its diplomatic strategy, and fosters economic collaboration, cultural confidence, social cohesion, and scientific and technological advancement. By implementing effective cultural communication strategies, China can play a more substantial role in globalization and promote world peace and development. To address existing obstacles, scholars have proposed various solutions. Jin and Jin (2023) highlight the importance of Chinese language education in South Korean universities to improve young people's intercultural communication skills and cultural identity. Additionally, China should develop an independent cultural industry to boost cultural exports (Liu, 2006) and improve the efficiency and transparency of its film censorship to address the legislative gap in cultural communication strategy with South Korea (Xu, 2021). On a micro level, scholars suggest that filmmakers should balance media differences, integrate cultural elements, align with contemporary cultural discourse, and address the target audience's emotional and ethical perspectives to ensure successful reception in diverse markets (Zhang & Nie, 2024). Wang and Wang (2022) recommend using diverse communication channels and creating popular science readings to foster a broader appreciation and understanding of Chinese literary masterpieces.

Previous research has primarily concentrated on the historical roots of cultural interactions between China and Korea and their consequences. However, there is a lack of robust investigation into the contemporary ramifications of the diffusion of Chinese culture in Korea and the factors that shape it. This study aims to address the existing research gap by conducting an empirical investigation. This study conducts a comprehensive analysis of Koreans' understanding and fascination with Chinese culture, as well as the impact of its dissemination. By combining survey data with existing literature, the study presents specific recommendations for enhancing the dissemination effects of Chinese culture in Korea. These recommendations are supported by empirical evidence, providing a solid basis for improvement.

2. Research Design

2.1 Subjects of the study

The subjects of this study are individuals of Korean nationality. A grand total of 181 questionnaires were obtained via an online survey, out of which 180 were deemed valid. The interviewees consisted of individuals from various educational and professional backgrounds in Korea, with 16.1% falling within the age range of 18-25 and 60.2% falling within the age range of 26-35. The age group of 36-45 represented 22 percent, while that of over 46 accounted for 1.7 percent. In general, there is a significant percentage of individuals who are young or in their middle age. The respondents encompass a diverse range of individuals, including students, education/researchers, culture/media practitioners, and individuals from various backgrounds. The majority of respondents were university students (54.2%), with master's degree holders (30.5%), doctoral degree holders (13.6%), and high school graduates (1.7%) comprising smaller proportions.

The surveyed population is stable, well-balanced, and representative of the research population that will be targeted in this study. These participants are capable of representing the general sentiment of young people in the Korean society towards Chinese culture.

2.2 Content of the Study

This study aims to investigate the impact of the dissemination of Chinese culture in Korea. The research in question encompasses the following two aspects. Firstly, the level of Korean people's understanding and interest with Chinese culture. The study focuses on examining the general perception of Chinese culture among the Korean population and their level of familiarity with specific aspects of Chinese culture. Furthermore, this pertains to the assessment made by Korean individuals regarding the impact of Chinese cultural exchange and their recommendations. The study extensively and thoroughly examined the impact of communication resonance, the major challenges in communication, and the extent to which the communication process has been fully acknowledged.

2.3 Methodology

This study employs a quantitative research methodology and gathers data through a comprehensive questionnaire. The questionnaire comprises inquiries that cover various aspects, including accessibility, overall perception, and familiarity with Chinese cultural intricacies, obstacles to comprehension, specific areas of interest, and dissemination effectiveness. Descriptive statistics were employed to analyze the data, and the gathered information was condensed and examined to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the Korean public's awareness and acceptance of Chinese culture.

3. Korean People's Perception of Chinese Culture

The investigation into Korean people's perception of Chinese culture focused on three main areas: overall impression, detailed perception, and cognitive barriers. To assess the overall impression, the questionnaire included questions about the ways Koreans understand Chinese culture, their evaluation of its overall impression, and their cognitive level regarding it. To explore the detailed perception, the questionnaire asked about the traditional content that best represents Chinese culture and the most favored Chinese festivals. For the cognitive barriers, respondents were directly asked to identify factors such as "language barriers", "cultural differences", "lack of channels", "difficulty in understanding content", and "other potential obstacles".

3.1 The general perception of Chinese culture among Korean people

The extent of Korean people's familiarity with Chinese culture is influenced by their exposure to Chinese cultural elements, their overall perception of Chinese culture, and their understanding of specific aspects of Chinese culture.

The findings of the questionnaire survey indicate that the primary source of Korean people's understanding of Chinese culture is news media (37.2%), followed by books and newspapers (18.9%), other means (18.3%), tourism activities (15%), and cultural lectures (10.6%).

Koreans primarily acquire knowledge about Chinese culture through the official news media, particularly the mainstream media in South Korea. Their initial exposure to Chinese culture occurs through local news reports and other channels, which is then followed by engaging in travel activities. A significant number of Koreans travel to China due to the geographical

proximity of the two countries. Furthermore, their initial encounter with Chinese culture occurred through printed media such as books and newspapers. A limited cohort of individuals were introduced to Chinese culture initially via foreign social media, Chinese songs, television, and films. This indicates that the dissemination of Chinese culture in South Korea is insufficiently extensive. The promotion on social media and other activities, in particular, is insufficient.

Regarding the overall impression of Chinese culture, 15% of individuals express a strong interest, 36.3% show a moderate interest, 30% lack interest, and 18.7% have no interest at all. In general, the Korean population's perception of Chinese culture exhibits a clear trend of polarization. Approximately 50% of the participants hold a favorable general perception of Chinese culture and exhibit a degree of curiosity towards it, thereby establishing a solid basis for the dissemination of Chinese culture in South Korea. Nevertheless, the remaining half of the participants displayed minimal enthusiasm towards Chinese culture, suggesting that there is ample opportunity for enhancing the dissemination of Chinese culture in South Korea.

According to the survey respondents, the Korean demonstrates a considerable level of awareness regarding Chinese culture. 52.3% of the participants selected the category "general," while 31.7% had limited knowledge on the subject, and 27% possessed a relatively high level of knowledge. Based on the provided data, it is evident that the Korean population's understanding of Chinese culture exhibits a distinct hierarchy. The majority of individuals possess a superficial and limited comprehension of Chinese culture, a significant portion of the population lacks awareness of it, and only a minority have a profound understanding of it. This indicates that there is a certain basis for the dissemination of Chinese culture in Korea, but further efforts are required to enhance its extent and scope. It is necessary to increase the scope of cultural dissemination and enhance awareness among this specific group of people through increased publicity and educational initiatives. Additionally, it is necessary to offer cultural activities of good quality in order to enhance their comprehension of Chinese culture.

3.2 The extensive understanding of Chinese culture among Korean people

The survey was conducted to assess the Korean people's understanding of the fundamental essence of Chinese culture and traditional cultural elements, with the aim of gaining insight into their knowledge of the Chinese spirit.

Poetry, music, and folk art are the traditional cultural elements that have gained greater recognition and acceptance among the Korean people. Specifically, 39.4% of the population acknowledges poetry, while 37.2% acknowledges music. This suggests that these cultural forms are more successful in capturing and maintaining the audience's attention due to their diverse nature, interesting content, and widespread distribution channels. While the percentage of individuals opting for calligraphy and Chinese painting is relatively low (16.7%), this particular group exhibits a greater level of appreciation and awareness towards the art. This suggests that calligraphy and Chinese painting hold a significant influence in the high-end cultural market.

The preferred festivals among Koreans are Chinese New Year (39.4%), Mid-Autumn Festival (13.3%), Dragon Boat Festival (7.6%), Lantern Festival (2.5%), and an uncertain percentage (39.7%) who are unsure about Chinese festivals. These statistics indicate that Chinese New Year, being the most significant traditional festival in China, holds a considerable level of recognition and attraction in Korea. The extensive impact of the Chinese New Year can be ascribed to the abundant cultural events, robust media campaigns, and targeted promotions in Sino-Korean cultural exchanges. In addition, South Korea is home to several Chinatowns where residents also partake in Spring Festival traditions such as posting spring couplets and hanging lanterns in their homes. The Mid-Autumn Festival has effectively promoted Chinese festival culture to the local population through these explicit celebrations. Nevertheless, the Mid-Autumn Festival, Dragon Boat Festival, and Lantern Festival are less well-known and embraced in comparison to the Spring Festival. Approximately 33% of the individuals surveyed expressed uncertainty regarding the traditional festivals celebrated in China. This indicates a lack of effective publicity and promotion of traditional Chinese festivals in Korea. Therefore, there is a need to improve cultural dissemination in order to enhance the Korean public's knowledge and understanding of traditional Chinese festivals.

Figure 3.2-1 Preferred Chinese Festivals among Koreans

3.3 Obstacles in comprehending Chinese culture

A separate survey was conducted to examine the obstacles faced by Korean individuals in comprehending Chinese culture. These barriers also serve as impediments to the dissemination of culture. The survey results indicate that the primary issue is the language barrier, accounting for 47.4% of the respondents' concerns. This is followed by cultural differences at 41.6%, while lack of channels and difficult-to-understand content account for 6% and 5% respectively. Communication can be hindered by multiple obstacles, with language barriers and cultural differences being the primary factors that need to be addressed in order to enhance communication effectiveness.

The Chinese culture has a long and intricate history, with abundant layers of meaning. For Koreans who are newly exposed to Chinese culture, comprehending these profound cultural foundations may appear overly complex and challenging. In addition, Koreans who are not acquainted with Chinese culture may find it challenging to comprehend various aspects of it, including ancient poems and calligraphy, which are considered classic works and cultural expressions. Another issue arises from the absence of clear instructions and explanations during the dissemination process. When it comes to disseminating Chinese culture, there is a dearth of effective guidance and explanation, resulting in numerous cultural elements being presented in a manner that is not easily comprehensible. This, in turn, amplifies the challenge of understanding.

Figure 3.2-2 Obstacles in Comprehending Chinese Culture

Currently, the channels through which Chinese culture is spread in Korea are quite limited, primarily relying on traditional media and sporadic cultural events. This approach falls short of fully utilizing modern technology and new media platforms for dissemination. Despite the existence of cultural exchanges between China and Korea, the frequency and extent of these exchanges remain inadequate to effectively reach the general public.

4. Assessment and Recommendations on Chinese Cultural Exchange

In the questionnaire survey, Korean people were evaluated on the effectiveness of Chinese cultural dissemination and provided suggestions for improving the dissemination process in Korea. The evaluation of the dissemination effect focused on four main aspects: “overall impact”, “level of resonance”, “difficulties and obstacles encountered during dissemination”, and

“adherence to the dissemination process”. For the communication suggestion survey, respondents were asked about effective channels, forms, methods of communication, and target audience groups. A multiple-choice format was used for the communication suggestions survey.

4.1 Assessment of the impact of Chinese cultural communication on the Korean population

The assessment of the dissemination impact primarily relies on four factors: “overall impact”, “level of resonance”, “difficulties and obstacles encountered during dissemination”, and “adherence to the dissemination process”. An investigation was conducted to determine if the communication process was fully respected. The findings are as follows.

The majority of respondents rated dissemination effectiveness as poor (42.7%), followed by fair (32.8%), good (12.2%), very poor (7%), and very good (5.3%). Approximately 50% of the participants hold the belief that the distribution of information is inadequate and requires substantial enhancement. This implies that the current methods of communication and content are inadequate in reaching and captivating this particular audience, highlighting notable deficiencies and the necessity for enhancement. 33.3% of the participants regarded the communication's effectiveness as average. The proportions of respondents who rated the effectiveness of Chinese culture communication as “very good” and “good” were approximately 17.5%, indicating that a small number of participants expressed satisfaction with it. The survey revealed that the majority of Koreans held a neutral stance towards the impact of Chinese culture, considering it to be average and lacking a profound impact.

Resonance levels were ranked in descending order based on percentage, with ‘average’ accounting for the highest percentage at 43.3%. Subsequently, there is a 23.9% occurrence of ‘a little resonance’, followed by 16.7% where no resonance is present, and finally 15% where there is a greater degree of resonance. The survey results indicate that a significant majority of the respondents (78.6%) had average or below average levels of resonance towards the dissemination content of Chinese culture. This suggests that the dissemination content failed to effectively resonate with the majority of the audience. Furthermore, it indicates that they possess certain emotional responses towards the content of Chinese culture, albeit not profound or intense enough. Consequently, there exists a discernible disparity in their level of acceptance of the culture.

To identify the most significant challenges in dissemination, a multiple-choice question is posed to the respondents, and the survey findings are as follows. The primary issue identified by the participants is the cultural disparity, constituting 54.4% of the responses. This indicates that Korean individuals are significantly impacted by the divergences in cultural origins and principles when engaging with and comprehending Chinese culture. Next, language barriers are reported at a rate of 30 percent, suggesting that differences in language significantly impact the communication and comprehension of cultural content. The homogenization of content was measured at 27.2%, which suggests a dearth of diversity and originality in the cultural content that is currently being conveyed. A total of 7.22% of the participants expressed concerns about the sole method of communication, indicating that the current communication channels are inadequate in effectively reaching and involving the target audience. The remaining individuals constituted 3.3 percent of the overall population. Additional concerns encompass limited opportunities for exposure, unfavorable impressions or attitudes towards China, discriminatory perceptions of Koreans, and international diplomatic relations. Respondents reported a dearth of familiarity with Chinese culture, which hampers their comprehension and enthusiasm for it. Due to the limited usage of social media and platforms like Google, Instagram, and YouTube in China, there is a scarcity of information about China on these platforms, and some of the available information is unfavorable. Consequently, the chance for Korean individuals to acquire knowledge about Chinese culture is diminished. Furthermore, due to the political rhetoric, South Korean media exhibits a greater tendency to disseminate adverse information regarding China, encompassing political conflicts and environmental issues. This inclination may foster bias against Chinese culture among the South Korean populace. For instance, the installation of the THAAD anti-missile system in South Korea in 2016 provoked a robust response from China, resulting in strained relations between the two nations and a decline in cultural interactions. Contrary to the abundance of negative news, there is a scarcity of positive reports and introductions regarding Chinese culture, leading to a restricted public comprehension of Chinese culture.

Figure 4.1-3 Challenges during the Dissemination

In the end, a survey has been conducted to determine the level of respect given to Chinese culture during the process of dissemination. The findings indicate that 45.4% of the participants hold the belief that Chinese culture is generally regarded with respect during its dissemination in Korea. The statement suggests that most Koreans acknowledge that while Chinese culture has been given a certain level of fundamental admiration during its spread, it still lacks in certain aspects and depth, leaving room for further enhancement. The proportion of individuals who did not receive adequate respect amounted to 38.8%, suggesting that a substantial segment of the Korean population harbors a more unfavorable perception regarding the level of respect for Chinese cultural communication. This segment of the audience may have experienced bias or misinterpretation in cross-cultural communication, resulting in their perception that Chinese culture has not received adequate reverence.

4.2 Recommendations regarding the promotion of Chinese culture

The primary focus of the dissemination suggestions revolved around the examination of dissemination channels, modes of dissemination, techniques of dissemination, and target audience segments. The multiple-choice question was adopted. According to the survey results, tourism projects are regarded as the most efficient means of communication, comprising approximately 53.9%. This implies that facilitating Korean tourists to directly engage with Chinese culture through tourism initiatives is the most appealing and efficient means of communication. Tourism programs offer direct interaction and firsthand experience of Chinese culture, which can amplify tourists' fascination and connection with Chinese culture. The mainstream media and cultural and creative industries follow, representing 41.7% and 35.0% respectively. This indicates that the spread of Chinese culture through mass media and innovative cultural products holds significant promise. The mainstream media has the ability to reach a wide range of audiences quickly and has a significant impact on them. The mainstream media holds significant credibility among a large number of individuals and has the ability to enhance the authoritative nature of communicated content. By utilizing films, animation, games, and other popular forms of entertainment, Chinese culture can be effectively disseminated and its global impact can be strengthened. Cultural and educational institutions comprise 22.8% of the total, highlighting the significance of imparting cultural knowledge to the younger generation through structured cultural education. Educational institutions exert a significant impact on the younger generation, fostering their curiosity and sense of belonging towards Chinese culture.

Figure 4.2-1 Dissemination Suggestions

Cultural exchange activities are regarded as the most effective means of dissemination, constituting approximately 56.7%. This suggests that the most appealing and efficient way to communicate is by directly showcasing and sharing Chinese culture through cultural exchange activities. Following that, cooperative school-running programs accounted for 17.8% of the total, suggesting that systematic education is a significant method for culturally disseminating information to international students. Sporting events and economic and trade exchanges constituted 12.6% and 10.0% respectively, suggesting that cultural diffusion through sports events and business exchanges also holds some promise.

Figure 4.2-2 Effective Dissemination Means

When it comes to methods of communication, digital museums and VR/AR technology are regarded as the most efficient ways to integrate modern technology and improve the effectiveness of Chinese cultural communication. They account for 26.8% and 26.1% respectively. This suggests that by utilizing digital museums, virtual reality, and augmented reality technologies, it is possible to create immersive cultural experiences and provide convenient access, thereby improving the dissemination of Chinese culture. The utilization of artificial intelligence and live interaction contributed to 24.6% and 22.0% of the results, respectively. This suggests that the promotion of Chinese culture in Korea can be significantly improved through the implementation of intelligent, customized cultural services and immediate interactive communication methods.

The two most significant audience groups for dissemination are university students and tourists, comprising 29.8% and 29.7% respectively. It suggests that promoting Chinese culture can be effectively achieved through higher education, cultural exchange activities, tourism programs, and cultural experience activities. Cultural practitioners constitute the second most significant category, comprising 16.4 percent of the overall total. This indicates that the dissemination and promotion of culture through professional avenues is also a crucial means of cultural expression. Although primary and secondary school students make up a smaller percentage (13.2%), it is crucial to cultivate their cultural awareness and interest through the education system in the long run.

The survey examined the concerns that the Korean public believes require attention when Chinese culture becomes globalized. The most significant factors to consider were the disparities in cross-cultural backgrounds and the improvement of audience engagement, accounting for 31.0% and 26.8% respectively. This implies that in order to improve the effectiveness of

communication when promoting Chinese culture, it is crucial to have a comprehensive understanding of and show respect for the diverse cultural backgrounds, as well as employ interactive methods of communication. The increase in the appeal of cultural content and the expansion of product variety contributed to 21.0% and 11.6% respectively. This suggests that international audiences can be effectively engaged by captivating and diverse cultural content.

5. Analysis and suggestions

5.1 Overview evaluation

This study aims to analyze the present state and impacts of the dissemination of Chinese culture in Korea. The results of the aforementioned research are analyzed and summarized into three primary aspects.

1.1.1 A need for enhancement in cultural awareness and interest

The survey results indicate notable disparities in Koreans' perception of Chinese culture. The majority of Koreans possess a certain level of familiarity with Chinese culture; however, the extent and scope of this knowledge are still inadequate. Even within the broad scope of cultural awareness, such as traditional festivals. Although there is a lack of knowledge about Chinese culture among some Koreans, over 50 percent of the respondents express either a "considerable" or "intense" interest in Chinese culture, suggesting a significant level of curiosity and eagerness to further explore Chinese cultural aspects. Nevertheless, there are still certain individuals who express a complete lack of interest or only a minimal interest in Chinese culture. This indicates that there is a need to enhance the appeal of cultural communication to cater to audiences with varying levels of interest.

5.1.2 A lack of effective communication and a low level of resonance

Despite widespread interest in Chinese culture, the impact and level of resonance are relatively low. Over 60% of respondents indicated an "average" or "low resonance" level, suggesting that Chinese culture fails to evoke emotional resonance and identification among Korean audiences during the cultural dissemination process. This suggests that Chinese culture has not effectively evoked strong emotional connection and identification among Korean during the communication process. This demonstrates that the current communication methods and content are insufficient in satisfying the requirements of the audience. In the future, cultural communication should prioritize enhancing the appeal and variety of content, expanding the scope and richness of culture, and catering to the diverse requirements of audiences across various levels.

5.1.3 Cultural disparities and linguistic obstacles impeding effective dissemination

The primary challenges faced in contemporary communication are cultural disparities and linguistic obstacles. Cultural disparities hinder the cultural resonance between the two sides during the dissemination process, leading to Koreans feeling unfamiliar and uneasy when exposed to Chinese culture. Additionally, the language barrier prevents them from fully comprehending and embracing the profound cultural implications of Chinese culture. The presence of these two hindrances has had a substantial impact on the dissemination of Chinese culture in Korea, necessitating the implementation of efficacious strategies to surmount them.

5.2 Suggestions

Considering the issues identified in the study's findings, the following suggestions are proposed to enhance the promotion of Chinese culture in Korea.

5.2.1 Streamline the cultural content and augment the appeal and variety of the cultural content

To effectively spread Chinese culture in Korea, it is imperative to offer culturally enriching content that is both accessible and comprehensible. The complexity of comprehending cultural content can be diminished through engaging and captivating modes of communication. The integration of music, games, fashion, science, and technology into the dissemination of Chinese culture serves to enrich the modes of expressing cultural content. Additionally, it helps to overcome language barriers, enhances the diversity and hierarchical nature of dissemination, and makes cultural transmission more dynamic and lifelike. Furthermore, contemporary cultural elements are incorporated alongside traditional culture. Contemporary culture possesses the attributes of style, originality, and engagement, which can successfully captivate the interest and involvement of the younger demographic, while also fostering greater understanding and diminishing the feelings of detachment and unease stemming from differences. It has the ability to disseminate Chinese culture in a more subtle manner. It is possible to create film and TV productions that depict the social life and culture of contemporary China. These productions can showcase the lifestyle, social transformations, and technological advancements of modern China, with the aim of making the cultural content more relatable to Korean audiences in their everyday lives.

Chinese culture can be made more appealing and captivating by incorporating engaging narratives, entertaining elements, and vibrant expressions. Create culturally diverse content tailored to the specific needs of audiences of various age groups.

Enhance the provision of guidance and elucidation on cultural content to facilitate audiences' comprehension and embrace of Chinese culture.

5.2.2 Integrate contemporary technology to broaden communication channels and amplify the interactivity of communication.

Utilize multimedia platforms to enhance the distribution channels and frequency of Chinese cultural dissemination, and extensively disseminate Chinese cultural content through television, the internet, social media, and other mediums. Utilize platforms like YouTube and other video-sharing websites to disseminate Chinese cultural content, including historical documentaries, cultural lectures, and travel videos, with the aim of captivating a larger audience. Alternatively, utilize popular social media platforms like Instagram and TikTok to share concise videos showcasing Chinese culture, aiming to engage and captivate younger viewers through enjoyable and interactive content. In addition, you can initiate challenges that revolve around Chinese culture (e.g. #DiscoverChina) or cultural challenges, such as cultural quizzes and handicraft challenges. These challenges aim to stimulate audience engagement and encourage them to share their accomplishments. By doing so, the content gains more visibility and becomes more interactive through active participation and sharing.

5.2.3 Facilitate immersive cultural experience programs to promote and enrich cross-cultural exchange and foster mutual understanding.

To foster greater mutual understanding and tolerance between the two populations and mitigate the challenges posed by cultural disparities, it is imperative to engage in additional cross-cultural exchange initiatives, such as cultural festivals, cultural exchange visits, and collaborative projects. Offer immersive cultural communication techniques, such as virtual reality (VR) cultural experiences and interactive cultural activities, to enhance audience engagement and provide a more authentic cultural experience. Utilize virtual reality (VR) technology to replicate China's historical sites and landmarks, including the Great Wall, the Forbidden City, and the Terracotta Warriors and Horses. This will enable audiences to embark on virtual tours of these cultural sites using VR equipment, immersing themselves in the magnificence and historical ambiance of these locations. One can also create virtual reality projects that offer cultural experiences, such as virtual festivals and reenactments of historical events. This allows viewers to participate in traditional festivals, major historical events, and other cultural experiences through virtual reality, thereby enhancing their cultural immersion. Virtual cultural workshops can be conducted online, allowing viewers to actively engage through live broadcasting or videoconferencing. This provides an opportunity to learn traditional Chinese skills, such as calligraphy, painting, and tea art, remotely.

5.2.4 Offer superior translation resources and expert elucidations to acquire a more profound comprehension of Chinese culture and mitigate misinterpretations.

To enhance the dissemination of Chinese culture in Korea, we should improve the availability of high-quality translation resources, including literature, audiovisual productions, and cultural initiatives. Collaboration with reputable translation agencies and linguistic specialists is essential to ensure precision and smoothness in translations. Additionally, increasing the availability of Chinese language courses and learning opportunities within the Korean education system is crucial. Offering scholarships and exchange programs can further incentivize students to pursue Chinese language acquisition. Employing contemporary technology, such as online language learning platforms, applications, and virtual classrooms, will provide more adaptable and convenient methods for language acquisition.

Engaging Korean cultural specialists in Chinese culture promotion initiatives can enhance communication by leveraging their unique perspectives and interpretations. Alternatively, inviting renowned Chinese scholars to deliver comprehensive lectures on Chinese history and culture at Korean universities and cultural centers can facilitate a deeper understanding of Chinese culture among Korean audiences.

Implementing these strategies can significantly strengthen the dissemination and impact of Chinese culture in South Korea, leading to enhanced mutual understanding and amicable relations between the two populations. Consistently striving for progress and enhancements can help Chinese culture achieve broader dissemination and global recognition, thereby enriching and diversifying world culture.

6. Conclusion

The study effectively demonstrates the multifaceted nature of Chinese cultural dissemination in South Korea, highlighting both the successes and the areas needing improvement. Through various channels such as educational exchanges, media collaborations, and cultural events, China has managed to significantly enhance its cultural influence and foster greater understanding between the two nations. However, the research also points out the challenges posed by cultural differences and the necessity for more nuanced and targeted approaches to maximize the effectiveness of these dissemination efforts. Future strategies should focus on deepening the engagement through localized content and sustained cultural dialogue to build a more robust and enduring cultural bridge between China and South Korea.

References

- Hu, X., McLean, D. (2020). Globalization and Cultural Diplomacy: China's Approach. *Global Policy*, 11(3), 350-364.
- Jin, H.M., Jin, G. Z. (2023). The Cultivation Strategies of Chinese Cultural Identity in Korean Language Teaching in Colleges and Universities. *Journal of Yanbian University (Social Sciences)*, 56(04): 75-81. [In Chinese: 金红梅, 金光洙, (2023). 高校韩国语教学中中国文化认同的培养策略. 延边大学学报(社会科学版), 56(04):75-81+143.]
- Jin, M. S., Wang, Q.Q. (2024). Chinese Writing in Korean Literature in the New Century. *Korean Teaching and Research*, (01):86-93. [In Chinese: 金明淑, 王倩倩. 新世纪韩国文学作品中的中国书写. 韩国语教学与研究, (01):86-93.]
- Jin, Y.H. (2020). On the "Going Out" of Culture through Chinese Elements in Korean Movies. *Journal of Lingnan Normal University*, 41(06):77-85. [In Chinese: 金艳红, (2020). 从韩国电影中的中国元素看文化如何“走出去”. 岭南师范学院学报, 41(06), 77-85.]
- Lee, J. (2020). The Korean Wave and Chinese Cultural Consumption. *Asian Cultural Studies*, 19(4), 301-319.
- Li, Y.Y., Yu, Q. (2023). The Construction of Chinese Elements in Korean Film and Television in Cross-cultural Perspective. *Press Outpost*, (18):24-26. [李媛媛, 禹晴. 跨文化视域下韩国影视作品对中国元素的构建. 新闻前哨, (18):24-26.]
- Liu, Y. (2019). China's Cultural Diplomacy and Soft Power in the Modern Era. *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 25(6), 672-688.
- Liu, Y. H. (2006). The Influence of Korean Film and Drama on Chinese Cultural Communication. *Journalism Lover*, (04):49. [In Chinese: 刘艳红, (2006). 韩国影视剧对中国文化传播的影响. 新闻爱好者, (04):49.]
- Piao, Y. Z., Du, S. S. (2010). On Wushu Culture International Communication Based on Confucius Institute Model: A Case Study of South Korea. *Journal of Shenyang Sport University*, 29(01):125-128. [In Chinese: 朴一哲, 杜舒书, (2010). 基于孔子学院模式的武术文化国际传播研究——以韩国为例. 沈阳体育学院学报, 29(01):125-128.]
- Pu, Z. P. (2002). The Dissemination and Development of Chinese Culture in South Korea. *Journal of Hanjiang Normal University*, (01):43-47. [In Chinese: 朴钟培, (2002). 中国文化在韩国的传播与发展. 汉江师范大学学报, (01):43-47.]
- Wang, Z., Wang, L. (2022). A Review of Studies on the Dissemination of Chinese TV Dramas in Vietnam and South Korea under High Context Cultures. *West China Broadcasting TV*, 43(20):108-110. [In Chinese: 王卓, 汪莉. 高情境文化下中国电视剧在越南和韩国传播的研究综述. 西部广播电视, 43 (20):108-110.]
- Xu, H. T. (2021). A Study of the Interaction between the Korean Film and Television Industry and the National Cultural Communication Strategy. *Journal of News Research*, 12(17):94-96. [In Chinese: 徐昊通. 韩国影视产业与国家文化传播策略的互动研究. 新闻研究导刊, 12 (17):94-96.]
- Xu, L.D., Kuang, W.L. (2019). The Dilemma and Strategies of Spreading Chinese Classical Culture: A Dream in Red Mansions as an Example to Illustrate the Frustration and Countermeasures of Telling Chinese Stories in Korea. *Journal of Dali University*, 4(07):62-66. [In Chinese: 中国古典文化输出窘境与策略——以《红楼梦》在韩国讲中国故事受阻与对策为例. 大理大学学报, 4 (07):62-66.]
- Zhang, Y., Nie, Z. T. Cross-media and Cross-cultural Exploration: A Study of Chinese Film Adaptation of Korean Web Comics. *Movie Literature*, (12):3-10. [In Chinese: 张燕, 聂在田. 跨媒介与跨文化的探索——韩国网络漫画的中国电影改编研究. 电影文学, (12):3-10.]
- Zheng, H. (2019). The Spread and Status of A-Ma Culture in Korea in the Context of "Chinese Culture Going Out". *Cultural Journal*, (01):52-54. [In Chinese: 郑慧, (2019). “中国文化走出去”背景下妈祖文化在韩国的传播及现状. 文化学刊, 2019, (01): 52-54.]

Appendix

중국 문화의 해외 전파 효과 및 신뢰도 현황 조사 설문지

선생님:

안녕하십니까! 바쁘신 가운데 귀한 시간을 내어 설문조사에 참여해 주셔서 감사합니다. 저희는 광둥외국어외무대학교 연구팀으로, 현재 중국 문화의 국제 전파에 관한 연구 프로젝트를 진행 중입니다. 이번 조사는 중국 문화가 해외에서 어떻게 전파되고 있으며, 그 전파 효과를 알아보는 것을 목표로 하고 있습니다. 설문 내용은 중국 문화의 세계적 영향력을 더욱 높이기 위한 참고 자료로 활용하고자 합니다.

귀하의 소중한 의견과 제안은 연구에 큰 도움이 될 것입니다. 본 조사는 학술 규범과 연구 윤리를 엄격히 준수하며 귀하가 제공한 모든 정보를 비밀로 유지하고 학술 연구 목적에만 사용할 것을 약속드립니다. 설문지는 익명으로

작성되며, 안심하게 작성하시면 됩니다. 귀하의 참여는 중국 문화와 한국 문화 교류에 중요한 기여를 할 것이며, 이에 진심으로 감사드립니다!

첫 번째 기본 정보

각 항목의 뒤에 있는 빈 칸은 글자 또는 숫자로 작성해 주시고, 선택 항목이 있는 경우 해당 답변에 체크해 주시기 바랍니다.

A. 기본 정보

1. 귀하의 국적은?

2. 귀하의 나이는?

A. 18-25 세 B. 26-35 세 C. 36-45 세 D. 46-60 세 E. 60 세 이상

3. 귀하의 최종 학력은?

A. 고등학교 이하 B. 전문대 C. 학사 D. 석사 E. 박사 이상

4. 귀하의 직업은?

A. 정부/공공 사업 B. 교육/연구 C. 금융/비즈니스 D. 문화/미디어 E. 의료/건강 F. 학생 G. 기타 (구체적으로 작성해 주세요: _____)

두 번째 주요내용

귀하의 실제 상황에 맞게 해당 답변에 체크해 주세요. 문제에 맞고 틀림은 없으니, 사실대로 작성해 주세요.

A. 전파 인식

1. 중국 문화를 처음 접한 경로는 무엇입니까?

A. 뉴스 매체 B. 문화 강좌 C. 관광 활동 D. 도서/신문 E. 기타 (구체적으로 작성해 주세요: _____)

2. 중국 문화에 대한 전반적인 인상은 어떻습니까?

A. 매우 관심이 있음 B. 관심이 있음 C. 보통 D. 별로 관심 없음 E. 전혀 관심 없음 (구체적으로 작성해 주세요: _____)

3. 중국 문화를 이해할 때 가장 큰 장애물은 무엇이라고 생각합니까?

A. 언어 장애 B. 문화 차이 C. 홍보 채널이 부족하다 D. 내용 이해 어려움 E. 기타 (구체적으로 작성해 주세요: _____)

4. 한국에서 대중들이 중국 문화에 대한 전반적인 인지도는 어떻습니까?

A. 매우 잘 앎 B. 잘 앎 C. 보통 D. 별로 알지 못함 E. 전혀 알지 못함 (구체적으로 작성해 주세요: _____)

5. 중국 문화의 어느 역사 시기에 가장 관심이 있습니까?

A. 상고 ~ 진한 B. 위진남북조 수당 C. 송원명청 D. 근현대 E. 전혀 모름

6. 세계 문화에서 중국 문화의 위치는 어떻게 생각합니까?
A. 매우 중요함 B. 중요함 C. 보통 D. 별로 중요하지 않음 E. 전혀 중요하지 않음
7. 중국 민족 정신의 핵심 내용은 무엇이라고 생각합니까? (복수 선택 가능)
A. 애국주의 B. 집단주의 C. 고생과 노력 D. 근검절약 E. 기타 (구체적으로 작성해 주세요: _____)

B. 내용 선호

8. 중국 문화의 다양한 측면 중 가장 관심 있는 것은 무엇입니까?
A. 문학/예술 B. 역사/문화 C. 철학/사상 D. 민속/풍속 E. 기타 (구체적으로 작성해 주세요: _____)
9. 중국 문화를 이해하기 위해 어떤 형태를 선호합니까? (복수 선택 가능)
A. 글 읽기 B. 영상물 C. 현장 체험 D. 전문가 설명 E. 기타 (구체적으로 작성해 주세요: _____)
10. 전통 문화 내용 중 중국 문화의 특징을 가장 잘 대표하는 것은 무엇이라고 생각합니까?
A. 시가/노래 B. 전통극/공연 C. 서예/국화 D. 고전 음악 E. 기타 (구체적으로 작성해 주세요: _____)
11. 현대 문화 내용 중 가장 매력적인 것은 무엇입니까?
A. 영화/드라마 B. 대중 음악 C. 현대 문학 D. 패션 디자인 E. 기타 (구체적으로 작성해 주세요: _____)
12. 중국의 전통 명절 중 가장 좋아하는 것은 무엇입니까?
A. 춘절 B. 원소절 C. 단오절 D. 중추절 E. 기타 (구체적으로 작성해 주세요: _____)
13. 중국의 전통 기예 중 가장 체험하고 싶은 것은 무엇입니까?
A. 경극 B. 태극 C. 서예 D. 다도 E. 기타 (구체적으로 작성해 주세요: _____)
14. 중국의 어느 지역을 가장 좋아합니까?
A. 베이징 B. 상하이 C. 시안 D. 광저우 E. 신장 F. 기타 (구체적으로 작성해 주세요: _____)
15. 중국 문화의 해외 전파 언어로 무엇을 희망합니까?
A. 중국어 B. 영어 C. 현지 언어 D. 다국어 결합 E. 기타 (구체적으로 작성해 주세요: _____)

C. 전파 평가

16. 현재 중국 문화의 한국 전파 효과는 어떻다고 생각합니까?
A. 매우 좋음 B. 좋음 C. 보통 D. 별로 좋지 않음 E. 매우 나쁨
17. 중국 문화 내용을 접할 때 얼마나 공감을 느끼십니까?
A. 완전히 공감함 B. 상당히 공감함 C. 보통 D. 약간 공감함 E. 전혀 공감하지 않음
18. 현재 중국 문화의 해외 전파에서 가장 큰 문제는 무엇이라고 생각합니까? A. 언어 장애 B. 문화 차이 C. 내용의 동질화 D. 전파 방식 단일 E. 기타 (구체적으로 작성해 주세요: _____)
19. 중국 문화가 해외에서 전파되는 과정에서 충분한 존중을 받았다고 생각합니까?

- A. 완전히 존중 받았음 B. 상당히 존중 받았음 C. 보통 D. 별로 존중 받지 않았음 E. 전혀 존중받지 않았음
20. 다른 나라의 문화와 비교할 때 중국 문화의 국제적 영향력은 어떻다고 생각합니까?
A. 매우 강함 B. 강함 C. 보통 D. 약함 E. 매우 약함 D. 전파 제안
21. 중국 문화가 세계로 나아가는데 어떤 점에 주의해야 한다고 생각합니까? (복수 선택 가능)
A. 문화 내용의 흥미성 향상 B. 문화 콘텐츠의 다양성 강화 C. 관중과의 상호작용 강화 D. 문화 간 배경 차이의 중요성 강조 E. 기타 (구체적으로 작성해 주세요: _____)
22. 중국 문화의 전파에 유리한 채널은 무엇이라고 생각합니까? (복수 선택 가능)
A. 주류 매체 B. 문화 교육 기관 C. 관광 프로젝트 D. 문화 창작 산업 E. 기타 (구체적으로 작성해 주세요: _____)
23. 중국 문화의 해외 전파에 어떤 대상 그룹에 주목해야 한다고 생각합니까? (복수 선택 가능)
A. 초/중학생 B. 대학생 C. 문화 종사자 D. 관광객 E. 기타 (구체적으로 작성해 주세요: _____)
24. 다른 국가의 국민이 중국 문화를 이해하는 데 어떤 형식이 가장 효과적이라고 생각합니까? (복수 선택 가능)
A. 문화 교류 활동 B. 협력 학술 프로그램 C. 스포츠 경기 D. 무역 교류 E. 기타 (구체적으로 작성해 주세요: _____)
25. 현대 기술과 결합하여 중국 문화의 전파 효과를 높이는 방법은 무엇이라고 생각합니까? (복수 선택 가능)
A. VR/AR 기술 B. 인공지능 C. 라이브 인터랙션 D. 디지털 박물관 E. 기타 (구체적으로 작성해 주세요: _____)
26. 중국 문화의 국제적 영향력을 높이기 위해 중국 문화 홍보에 다른 제안이 있습니까? 있으시면 빈칸에 써주세요.